

RESEARCH IMPACT AND POLYCRISIS: NOTES, REFLECTIONS, AND A REMINDER OF THE ACADEMIC QUEST

Workshop Paper

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Abstract

The essence of the academic quest lies in asking questions out of intellectual curiosity. However, the question of research impact often leads Information Systems (IS) researchers to question if IS research concerns itself with academic fancies rather than ‘real-world’ problems. The ‘real-world’ phrase moves the lifeworld of academia outside the lifeworlds of society (and practice) and undermines the value that the academic quest has for society. Reflecting on my experiences against the discourse on IS research impact, I hope to inspire to emancipate ourselves from this caging notion of research impact and seek to remind us of the importance of asking questions out of intellectual curiosity.

Keywords: Research impact, Lifeworld, Academic quest, Intellectual curiosity, Polycrisis

1 Preamble

Every now and then live-events prompt us to pause and contemplate the purpose and meaning of our actions. We may ponder them in relation to personal matters or broader societal issues. We may even ask ourselves about the impact of our actions on society. Especially now, in times of polycrises, I believe, we all have such moments, and I believe that they are important moments for making sense of our own choices but also for how our actions relate to and reach into the worlds of others and vice versa.

When such moments arise in the lifeworld of academia, we often ask what the impact of academia is, or let alone our very own research. Of all ponderings, this is among the most daunting. Academia is indeed a lifeworld of its own but not detached, rather entangled in many ways. We study other peoples’ lifeworlds to understand these worlds, to ask and answer the question: what is going on. However, we enter their lifeworlds not for free. There is by no doubt a contractual understanding that if we are allowed access, we should disclose what we discovered, and what we discovered should be of use not only to us and our academic discourse but also to those in the lifeworlds that we study. Often this matter of ‘research being of use’ seems to drive our discussion about research impact (Benbasat & Zmud, 1999; Pan & Pee, 2020; Wiener et al., 2018). However, if we define research as impactful only if it is of immediate use in the lifeworlds of practice or society—often referred to as the ‘real-world’ (Mathiassen, 2017; Nunamaker et al., 2017)—we undermine or even devalue the essence of academia. This essence lies in the quest of asking questions out of intellectual curiosity, out of the desire of *verstehen* (en: to understand). Separating between the real-world and academia renders the latter the unreal world, the illusory, and the academic quest the fanciful. Something academics do in their ivory towers to entertain themselves but of no use to—or with no impact on—the real world. Hence, by defining research as impactful if it is of immediate use to others in their lifeworlds, we run risk of peeling our own lifeworld to be the unreal or fanciful, which eventually leads to pondering: why should it exist?

I suggest that this existential question of ‘why academia’ strikes close to how we grapple with the concept of research impact both on a grand and small scale. That is, we—as academics and researchers—face this question as a collective and as individuals. Thus, the matter of research impact is both personal and societal. Therefore, I close this preamble describing my choice for academia before I explore the discourse on research impact among Information Systems (IS) scholars. Afterwards, I reflect my own practices for research impact against this discourse. Yet I do not position my reflections or

reminder against a specific argument on research impact but rather against the risk to succumb to forces towards evaluating academia mostly against its practice impact. Lastly, I engage with the question of research in times of polycrisis before closing with a reminder of the academic quest and a call to emancipate ourselves from the caging notion of research impact meaning immediate practice impact.

Following a practice-oriented university education in Germany, which included job placements in IT management, HR, vocational training, and research and development, I joined the University of Turku, Finland, as a research assistant and then industrial PhD. In my PhD studies, I investigated the digital transformation of a German car manufacturer while also consulting for this company. Afterwards, I joined Leuphana University Lüneburg, Germany, as a postdoctoral researcher, and later the University of Agder, Norway, as an Associate Professor. Thus, to this point, I have spent half my career in practice and half in academia.

Having gained lived experiences in both lifeworlds, I chose academia because of what I earlier referred to as its essence. I was intrigued by the possibility of asking the question of ‘what is going on’. My impression was that in practice, the focus was on finding solutions. Why or how they worked, what the underlying problem was, or the immediate or long-term consequences, all this seemed secondary to solving. Academia, on the other hand, appeared to offer the freedom to ask almost any question and engage in understanding for its own sake, without necessarily grasping the potential knowledge’s immediate practical use. This might imply I imagined academia as free from making an impact beyond its own lifeworld, which is not the case. Yet I did not place the sole purpose of existence of academia with the production of instrumental knowledge, but the quest of *verstehen* driven by intellectual curiosity.

2 Research impact in and of Information Systems research

The debate on IS research’s impact is closely linked to the discipline’s existence. It emerged in the 90s after IS established conferences, journals, and other structures to promote scientific rigour and by this also cleared itself as a research discipline. (Benbasat & Weber, 1996; Benbasat & Zmud, 1999; Robey, 1996). While since then, this debate has evolved, the key arguments and positions remain.

2.1 Synthesising three key arguments on research impact

From the IS debate on research impact, I synthesise three key arguments. These are the importance of addressing relevant issues, the question of who is the audience of our research, and the paradoxical nature of academic and practice impact. For each, I summarise different positions.

The first argument suggests that impactful IS research emerges from research that engages with relevant issues; the often labelled ‘real-world’ issues. (Mathiassen, 2017; Nunamaker et al., 2017). This argument implies that research can only have impact if at the time of setting the research design, the proposed research deals with what the ‘real-world’—whichever lifeworld the real one may be—flags as relevant (Wiener et al., 2018). Proponents countering this argument often advocate two things. First, many innovations stem from research that was considered irrelevant at the time of its execution (Wiener et al., 2018). Second, technological development entails that what practice considers relevant can change in an instant. Thus, chasing practice bears the risk of becoming fad-chasers, a risk that ultimately impedes the academic notion of cumulatively advancing knowledge for the betterment of society.

A second argument refers to the audience, the lifeworlds that we seek to contribute to. In the founding years, IS research seemed concerned with the lifeworlds of IS management. Accordingly, the definition of impact—and what impact IS should have—rested almost solely on solving organisational problems with IS, or solving IS related organisational problems (Benbasat & Weber, 1996; Benbasat & Zmud, 1999; Buhl et al., 2012). However, the audience has widened significantly as IS started to enter new lifeworlds like policymaking, societal, or individual IS use. Instead of only figuring out how to design, implement, and use IS in organisations, we increasingly concern ourselves with understanding how IS changes society or individuals’ behaviour (Wiener et al., 2018).

The third key argument concerns the paradoxical nature of knowledge in academia and practice. The academic and practice lifeworlds produce and value different types of knowledge. The different speeds of academic practice (e.g., journal publishing processes) and developments in technology and organisational practices make this seem like an unresolvable paradox. The positions towards this stretch from simplifying academic language for accessibility (Benbasat & Zmud, 1999; Wiener et al., 2018) to objecting this sacrifice of academic practice (or in consequence academia) (Lyytinen, 1999) but suggesting the practising of knowledge transfer through, for example, different forms of dissemination, practice collaboration, training PhD students who have prior practice experience, or even PhD programmes that involve practice partnerships (Klein & Rowe, 2008; Mathiassen, 2017; Nunamaker et al., 2017).

Further dissecting these three arguments, we can notice that the discourse on research impact has built on assumptions that both nurture and limit it. Firstly, it aspires that IS research has immediate practical impact by offering applicable solutions to real-world problems. Secondly, it mainly refers to the impact of IS research on other lifeworlds than academia. Thirdly, the problematised lack of this impact seems to boil down to different forms of knowledge and knowledge production in academia and practice.

2.2 Practising research impact: reflections from my own work

The heading already implies that I view research impact as something that we practice as knowledge transfer, and not as something that our research has or possesses. Accordingly, I recount and discuss examples of my own practising of knowledge transfer. However, I start describing my choice of research topic (or problem), which sets up conditions for, but does not constitute knowledge transfer itself.

My research focuses on phenomena of organisational transformation, because I have a curiosity for understanding how transformation unfolds and conceive it as a constant—the world is always changing—and possible catalyst towards the better. In my doctoral research, I studied the digital transformation of a business organisation. Personally, I view this research stream as classic IS, tuned towards the lifeworlds of business and IS practitioners. When I graduated, I pondered on how to develop my research portfolio. I desired to engage in something that would not only help businesses in tackling business issues to eventually serve their financial performance. I desired to engage in something that had the potential to contribute to the greater good. While I still believed in the power of transformation, a mere business-focused understanding of digital transformation seemed short of that ‘greater good’.

At that time, the sustainability crisis—as one crisis of the polycrisis (Lawrence et al., 2024)—was at the forefront of practitioners’ and policymakers’ minds. While the idea of combining digital and sustainability transformation existed, our understanding of how such co-transformation could work or what interrelated problems this creates (i.e., problems that—in the spirit of polycrisis—only come into sight if we view digital and sustainability transformation as one), was limited. Intrigued by the flavour that this added to my previous research and enthusiastic about the underlying objective, I decided to study digital–sustainable co-transformation. Thus, in the very sense of the existing discourse on IS research impact, I chose a research problem that I considered interesting but that I also felt as relevant to society.

My work on this new research stream started with figuring out conceptually what this co-transformation was and how I would position it in the existing digital transformation discourse (e.g. Zimmer & Järveläinen, 2022). This led me to the question how co-transformation was different from digital transformation and how this difference mattered. A question that I sought answering by engaging with the concepts of criticality, responsibility, and values. However, my approach was not ivory-tower contemplation. I chose to initiate research to mobilise our community and stimulate my own thinking. For example, I co-organised a workshop at ICIS 2022 that we developed into a special issue on embracing contrarian thinking and value-reflexivity in the *European Journal of Information Systems* (Zimmer et al., 2026). I co-authored an editorial on responsible digital transformation (Zimmer et al., 2023), an essay collection on digital responsibility (Trittin-Ulbrich et al., 2025), and conducted empirical research on co-transformation. Originally, I conceived the co-transformation notion from observations during my doctoral research. However, considering these observation’s for-profit business context, I wondered about co-transformation in other contexts (e.g., digital startups or non-profit organisations). Luckily, through my

network, I met Greenpeace who were interested in understanding their own co-transformation, and in sharing their insights with other organisations. We set up a research collaboration that resulted—for now—in a case study report on Greenpeace’s co-transformation (Zimmer et al., 2024), keynotes at Greenpeace events, and joint workshops for sharing and discussing our research insights with a wider audience. In this collaboration, two things surprised me.

First, Greenpeace appreciated my analytical and conceptual work. While I felt pressured to balance my academic interests and to translate my research into something immediately useful for Greenpeace, they did not expect readily applicable solutions. They appreciated my analytical work because it offered them frameworks for fathoming what is going on, what they are currently doing, or how what they do aligns (or does not). They used these insights to debate and negotiate their next actions. In another context, a PhD student, colleague, and I received similar feedback. After analysing a set of interviews, we summarised our key insights in a research dossier. The interview partners appreciated this dossier and the analytical framework and vocabulary that it contained. The conceptualisations resonated with them and helped them grasp their organisational situation, which ultimately serves their decision-making.

Second, when I entered my collaboration with Greenpeace, I had underestimated the power of mediate impact. Yet my Greenpeace counterparts told of how they used the results of our collaboration—or even my research outputs outside this collaboration—in their campaigning work or educational material.

Besides these examples, which appear to refer to the grand scale of research impact, I wish to emphasise illustrations of impact in the small. Personally, I find it most rewarding to observe the personal and intellectual growth in students. That is, for me, educational impact counts as much as academic or practice impact. Moreover, they—our students—can become multipliers and thus a vessel for mediate impact. Similarly, I enjoy observing the impact that my community service has. For example, I rejoice in observing the publication of research that I may have contributed to as an editor or reviewer. The point I wish to subsume: we should not only concern ourselves with the grand scale of impact but also with the small scale, the things that reside closer to what we can influence and observe.

Against the synthesised assumptions on IS research impact, I wish to highlight four reflections. First, my Greenpeace collaboration illustrates the conceptual relevance of research (cf. Nicolai & Seidl, 2010). Despite the widespread demand for immediately useful solutions, my example demonstrates that practitioners value analytical frameworks that help them comprehend their problems and make informed decisions or develop solutions. Note that this still requires knowledge transfer, but this observation elevates the currency of academic—or analytical, theoretical—knowledge for practice.

Second, my research on responsible digital transformation and co-transformation initiated further research. This in return generated knowledge or led to research offering solutions to practice and society. This, underlines that academic impact can serve as the precursor for practice impact (cf. Karanasios, 2022; Pan & Pee, 2020). This suggests that research impact does not equal practice impact but comprises of academic and practice impact (and one could add educational impact).

Third, my collaboration with Greenpeace demonstrates that research can have immediate and mediate impacts. My research had immediate impact on Greenpeace, and they further disseminated it in their network. Similarly, researchers drawing or building on our work can create mediate impact. This notion of mediate impact emphasises the importance of knowledge transfer through practice collaboration and highlights the value of academic impact. (cf. Mathiassen, 2017; Pan & Pee, 2020).

Finally, I should consider that my experience of knowledge transfer leading to significant impact or practitioners valuing analytical frameworks may be due to the nature of my knowledge transfer partner, Greenpeace. However, my experience with a PhD student and a colleague shows that appreciating ‘raw’ academic knowledge does not depend on the collaboration partner’s nature, but on our openness to listen and understand each other’s lifeworlds and knowledge. Nonetheless, I believe that this reminds us to consider how our choice of collaboration partners influences knowledge transfer and our impact.

3 Information Systems research in times of polycrisis

In the preamble, and when reflecting my research and knowledge transfer practices on digital–sustainable co-transformation, I referred colloquially to polycrisis. Yet how—or when—does IS research investigate a polycrisis or assume a polycrisis perspective? To answer this question, and why or how polycrisis matters for IS research and research impact, we must first—following the essence of academia—ask what is polycrisis, or ‘what is going on’ that people refer to a polycrisis.

Complexity researchers refer to ‘polycrisis [as] any combination of three or more interacting systemic risks that produces a single, emergent crisis’ (Janzwood & Homer-Dixon, 2022, p. 6). Thus, a polycrisis spans systems and refers to highly complex, inter-system issues that require simultaneous solutions. In this vein, supply chain issues, social welfare crises, international conflicts, the climate crisis, etc. can jointly constitute a polycrisis (Janzwood & Homer-Dixon, 2022; Seyd, 2025).

Considering this definition, I dare say that at face value, polycrisis does not appear as an IS phenomenon. However, I nonetheless intend to challenge this interpretation by asking two questions. Firstly, can polycrisis be understood as an IS phenomenon? Beyond face value, I would still argue that, in its original meaning, polycrisis does not *per se* refer to an IS phenomenon. The concept stems from complexity and sociology research referring to crisis and inter-systems risks that not necessarily emerge from IS (or their use). However, IS phenomena can indeed be part of this (or a) polycrisis. For example, fake news, hate speech, online propaganda, etc. all threaten democracy, information on international conflicts, social welfare, etc. Hence, while not *per se* an IS phenomenon, IS phenomena are part of the inter-system issues or may intensify them. In fact, IS research streams exist, for example on crisis management, business continuity (e.g., Järveläinen et al., 2022), or Green IS and digital–sustainable co-transformation (e.g., Zimmer & Järveläinen, 2022), that clearly link to inter-system issues that are part of polycrisis. Thus, a polycrisis may not be an IS phenomenon, but IS phenomenon may be part of a polycrisis.

Secondly, if IS phenomena are part of a polycrisis, how—or should—this shift our perspective on these phenomena? Polycrisis elevates inter-system risks over intra-system risks. However, IS research, because of the page limits of journals, tends to narrow down research problems. This often leads to granular, nicely compound, and internally coherent research insights focused on one specific system (or intra-system issues). Put differently, this leads to simplifications by cutting away complexity in a divide and conquer approach. For example, instead of studying the inter-system issues of digital and sustainability transformation, we often find work that assumes that digital is the solution to sustainability issues. However, digital is itself a sustainability issue (Zimmer et al., 2024). Polycrisis makes us aware of the complexity of systems and the need to study precisely this complexity. If IS research wants to understand and resolve inter-system issues that cause or contribute to a polycrisis, it must therefore adapt theories and methods attuned to assessing, dissecting, and explaining these issues. Researching polycrisis asks IS researchers to return to their discipline’s roots in system sciences and to embrace inter-system complexity in studying IS phenomena.

4 Conclusion: a reminder of the academic quest

Closing, I intend to remind us of the academic quest that renders IS a research discipline. This quest seeks knowledge to enlighten society. However, the debate on research impact often seems to spring from an urge towards more immediate impact on IS practice, as in applicable solutions. Reflecting my knowledge transfer practices, I shared that practitioners not only value instrumental but also conceptual knowledge, that practice impact also succeeds academic impact, and to not underestimate mediate research impact. I hope that my reminder of the academic quest and reflections inspire emancipation from the caging notion that research impact means immediate practice impact. Instead, research impact should mean societal impact, which can emerge from academic, educational, and practice impact. In this equation of societal impact, the academic lifeworld does not exist outside the ‘real-world’ or as a mere servant to business and economy, but constitutes an integral, and independent lifeworld of and for our societies. Moreover, I hope to inspire emancipation from the fixation on grand-scale over small-scale research

impact. Not to discourage or denounce the pursuit of the former, which requires time, the practice of knowledge transfer, and a good portion of luck, but to rejoice in the latter, the impact we can have on our direct environment, and to build from there.

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